

GENERATIVE DESIGN FOR CONSTRUCTABILITY IMPROVEMENTS WITH BIM|LEAN APPROACH

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Supervisors

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Abstract

The construction industry suffers from the lack of adoption of advanced technologies. As a consequence, construction is among the least productive industries across various sectors. The researchers often point out that the critical issue is the lack of integration throughout the building project life cycle. Lack of information integration causes reworks unexpected changes, lower construction quality, delays, and on-site conflicts, which could be addressed in advance by a proper constructability study executed already in the design phase. Constructability is a technique that examines the logic of construction from the beginning to the end, seeking technical solutions that reduce project cost, time, and waste. The central part of the thesis provides a comprehensive overview and analysis of non-technical and technical constructability issues. Special attention is given to Lean and BIM approaches, which may serve as driving mechanisms that substantially improve constructability. The presented work tries to identify the value and integration of mechanisms for the improvement of constructability issues. Among the technical issues, the rationalization of the design plays an essential role in improving the execution and reducing project costs and delays.

The final part of the thesis focuses on the rationalization of design addressing constructability issues by employing Generative Design. This approach is demonstrated in a case study of a complex building –Stožice Arena. The Arena case study shows the design rationalization techniques using generative design and machine learning, enabling informed shaping and clustering of the building envelope. The presented solution contributes to the evolving field of future architectural-structural design methods.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-JoseHernandez-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/HUJRYBBG5dq>

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